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Feminization of Statues in Longmen Grottoes during the Northern Wei Dynasty and its Causes

Zheng Xiaoxue

Abstract

During the Northern Wei Dynasty, the Longmen Grottoes in Luoyang were excavated, following the excavation of the Yungang Grottoes in Datong. When comparing the statues in the Longmen Grottoes and the Yungang Grottoes, the most prominent difference is that the statues in the Longmen Grottoes present different feminine features. First, the donor figures originally carved on both sides of the inscription on the statue corresponded to men and women, and a special arrangement appeared in the grottoes; second, there are female-centered pictures of worshipping Buddha in the Huangfugong Grottoes; and finally, the statues of Bodhisattvas carved in the caves show feminine characteristics, etc. The period of prosperous female statues in Longmen Grottoes coincided with when Empress Dowager Hu's power was extremely inflated, and temple construction was also very popular. During the same period, the female figurative sculptures in the Longmen Grottoes share numerous similarities with the Buddhist statues unearthed from the Yongning Temple Pagoda. Both the cave sculptures and temple construction reflect the societal context and political situation of the era, with the feminine attributes portrayed in the sculptures likely influenced by the political power of Empress Dowager Hu.

Key Words

Longmen Grottoes, Northern Wei, female figurative sculptures, Empress Dowager Hu

Introduction

After Emperor Xiaowen of the Northern Wei Dynasty moved his capital to Luoyang, the excavation of grottoes started. The Longmen Grottoes were the first site excavated in Luoyang. The grotto sculpture activities were active until the Northern Wei Dynasty split. Compared with the previously excavated Yungang Grottoes, there were many changes in the Northern Wei statues in the Longmen Grottoes. In addition to the changes in the combination, form, and content of the statues, another outstanding detail is that the feminization of the statues is very obvious. The feminized representation of statues refers to the statues that appear in male form in the Yungang Grottoes, but mostly in female form in the Longmen Grottoes. New forms of feminine statues also appeared in the

Longmen Grottoes. This article intends to clarify the feminine manifestations of the Northern Wei statues in the Longmen Grottoes and analyze the reasons behind them based on systematically sorting the statues of the Northern Wei Dynasty in the Longmen Grottoes.

1. Statues of Female Donors

The donor statue is an important part of the sculpture activities in the grotto. They are meritorious statues painted by donors who contributed material and financial resources to creating cave statues. In addition, there are also supporting statues carved as decoration. The donor portrait is usually presented in sculpture, painting, or other forms in Buddhist activities with special religious significance. In the sculpture art of the Longmen Grottoes, the donor portraits were usually

carved on both sides of the inscription under the Buddha niche, and a few appeared on the side of the statue niche or were carved separately as decoration. The number and location of these statues are often carefully considered to demonstrate the status of the statue maker. Most supporting figures are carved corresponding to men's and women's left and right sides. To present a sense of balance and harmony, occasionally, there are some independent supporting figures, or symbols of the images of senior monks and nobles. The statue of a female donor in the grotto is usually carved under the niche corresponding to the figure of a male donor, but there are also cases of female donors. In contrast, the statues of female donors in the Longmen Grottoes changed greatly from those in the Yungang Grottoes. To facilitate the discussion, the statues with female donors in the Longmen Grottoes during the Northern Wei Dynasty are classified into A, B, C, D and E types according to the number of combinations.¹

Type A is a single-person group, mainly distributed in the Guyang Cave and Huangfugong Cave. Taking the Guyang Cave as an example, male and female providers are on both sides of the statue niches, wearing Hu clothes. The Guyang Cave is the earliest dug in the Longmen Grottoes. It can be seen from the costumes of the providers that they were carved during the early stage of Emperor Xiaowen's reform, and the sinicized costumes were not fully popularized in the statue-making activities (figure 1).

Type B is a two-person group, mainly distributed in

the Lotus Cave, and there are also individual statues in the Putai Cave and the Guyang Cave. In this type, the original form of male and female donors has changed, and only female donors are carved under some statue niches. Using the N23 niche of the Lotus Cave as an example, it can be seen from the costumes that the four donor statues are all female (figure 2). Type C is a group of three people, almost all carved in the Lotus Cave, and what is more distinctive is that the front of the donor under the N48 statue niche is not carved bhikhu, and now the visible six bodies are all secular donors' figures (figure 3).

Type D is a combination of four or more people, and most of this type of donor ranks are carved in the Guyang Cave. Different from the common male and female separate statue niches on both sides, there are several special combinations of Buddha statues, such as the N263 statue niches in the Guyang Cave, named "Buddha Disciple Chang Hanjing (常汉敬) Statue Niches." The inscription on the statue and the donors' image are all engraved on the right side of the statue niche, and the five donors are facing the direction of the Buddha statue in two teams. A monk leads in front, followed by four female donors. Two women in the upper and lower teams hold lotus flowers, have double bun hairstyles, and wear cross-necked long skirts that drag the floor (figure 4). The queue of donors is divided into upper and lower rows in statue niche S27 in the Guyang Cave (figure 5). A statue niche is carved under the statue on the left side of niche S27, and a similar one

Figure 1. Figures of worshipers in the Guyang Cave. From *Guyang Cave: Cave 1443 of Longmen Grottoes*.

Figure 2. Female donor figures in niche N23 of the Lotus Cave, from *Cave 712 of Longmen Grottoes*.

also appeared in niche N246 (figure 7); it is speculated that the statues of the donors that were originally carved were destroyed in the later statue niches and then carved again, which led to the inconsistency between the left and right of the donor statues under the S27 niche and the N246 niche. In addition, the N263 Chang Hanjing statue niche is only engraved with five statues of supporting figures on the right side. Corresponding to the content of the inscription on the statue, “the lay follower, Chang Hanjing, along with his family members, totalling five, devoutly attend to the Buddha,” there may be insufficient carving space on the left side of the statue niche. It is possible to engrave the portrait of the offering person on the right side.

Type E is a row of donors composed of several men and women, and the Guyang Cave is the only example. Although the donor image is destroyed by the words “Guyang Cave”, the human features can still be distinguished from the remaining images: the female donor holding a three-petal lotus flower and the male donor holding various kinds of tribute, and the queue is orderly, and the direction is the same indicating that the female donor is in the same position as the male donor (figure 6). There are so many people, and they hold various kinds of Buddha offerings, which are beyond the reach of ordinary civilians and nobles—this is where the strong implication of imperial power in the statues in the Guyang Cave comes from.

In general, most of the combinations and arrangements of the donor figures are carved on both sides of the inscriptions of the statues in the form of male and female correspondence, and there are carved multiple rows of donor figures. For example, the forty-eight statues of male and female supporters carved under the “Guyang Cave” inscription may have a stronger decorative meaning. There are also cases where the number and queue of supporting portraits on both sides of the statue

niche do not correspond, which may be the flexible adjustment made by the artisans according to the actual situation at that time, or it may be related to the willingness of the donors.

In addition to the above combinations of female donors, a female-dominated ritual diagram queue can be used as a typical analysis in the Huangfugong Cave in the Longmen Grottoes. The cave is located in the south part of the west mountain of the Longmen Grottoes. It is named Huangfugong Cave because of the statue tablet “Taiwei Huangfugong Grottoes” (太尉公皇甫公石窟碑) on the south wall. The content of the inscription at the end makes it clear that the date of the opening of the grottoes is the third year of Xiaochang (527 AD) of the Great Wei Dynasty. According to records, HuangFu du was Empress Dowager Hu’s uncle, so it is speculated that the excavation of Huangfugong Cave was probably closely related to Empress Dowager Hu.

The main wall (west wall) of the Huangfugong Cave features an altar adorned with one Buddha, two disciples, four Bodhisattvas, and two Yakshas. The central Buddha figure has a boat-shaped body with a radiating aura. The upper section is embellished with flame motifs, while the lower part depicts honeysuckle patterns and four Bodhisattva images in acts of offering. On the inner sides, the disciple figures and the attendant Bodhisattvas stand upon lotus pedestals. The outer side’s Bodhisattva figures possess circular halos, with one hand resting on the knee and the other touching the leg, each seated in a relaxed pose. Inside the canopied niche on the south wall of the Huangfugong Cave, there is one Buddha, two Bodhisattvas, and two disciples. Below the niche, a relief carving portrays devotees in adoration. A total of seventeen figures are depicted, converging towards the center. In the center, a supporting Yaksha figure is sculpted, holding a rectangular tray containing an incense burner and a lotus-shaped offering. On the eastern side of

Figure 3. Figures of worshippers in niche N48 of the Lotus Cave, from *Cave 712 of Longmen Grottoes*.

Figure 4. Image of the donor in niche N263 of the Guyang Cave, as drawn by the author, from *Guyang Cave: Cave 1443 of Longmen Grottoes*.

Figure 5. Image of the donor in niche S27 of the Guyang Cave, as drawn by the author, from *Guyang Cave: Cave 1443 of Longmen Grottoes*.

Figure 6. "Guyang Cave" inscription and line drawing of the portrait of the donors as drawn by the author.

Figure 7. The queue of donors in niche N246 of the Guyang Cave, from *Guyang Cave: Cave 1443 of Longmen Grottoes*.

the relief, seven devotees proceed westward, led by a Bhikshu, followed by a male devotee, three attendants holding umbrellas and fans, and two indistinct figures. On the western side, the line of worshippers is led by another Bhikshu, followed by a male devotee wearing a high crown and a luxurious wide-sleeved coat, possibly indicating a royal identity. Male and female devotees stand together, some holding lotus flowers or umbrellas, while others hold the master's clothing closely behind (figure 8).

The devotional image beneath the alcove on the north wall predominantly centers on female figures. This depiction showcases fifteen worshippers measuring 0.7 meters high and 1.6 meters wide. At the forefront, three Bhiksunis lead the assembly, followed by a woman attired in luxurious clothing. She holds a lotus bud and is dressed in a wide-sleeved, collared robe with a waist sash, with a fragrant pouch hanging from her waist, while her floor-length skirt trails behind her. Behind the noblewoman stand three attendants: one holds her garments, two

Figure 8. Rubbing of the picture of worshipping Buddha on the south wall of the Huangfugong Cave. From *Longmen Grottoes Lower Part Huangfugong Grottoes*.

Figure 9. The figure of worshipping Buddha on the north wall of the Huangfugong Cave. From *Longmen Grottoes Lower Part Huangfugong Grottoes*.

hold feather fans, and another holds a decorative canopy. All three share the hairstyle of double-bun chignons. Following the noblewoman's quartet, a group of five individuals is led by a young man and a young woman. Smaller attendants accompany the central figures. The young man wears a towering crown and holds a lotus bud similar to the noblewoman's in his left hand, while supporting an alms bowl with his right hand. The young woman has a double-horned headdress, a round-collared, wide-sleeved upper garment, and a long skirt with a trailing sash. Her left hand extends forward, and her right hand supports an alms bowl. The procession's final trio features a slightly turned figure holding an upturned lotus, another holding a lotus bud, and a third holding a spherical object behind them (figure 9).²

The earlier representations of Buddhist rituals during the Northern Wei period can be observed within the Bingyang Central Cave at the Longmen Grottoes, with corresponding carvings of emperor Xiaowen's paying respect to Buddha depiction and empress Wenzhao's paying respect to Buddha illustration within the cave complex; the Buddha statues in the Gongxian Grottoes Temple were carved later, and the male-centered Buddha statues and female-centered Buddha statues were also carved accordingly. When the artisan painted or sculpted the donor figure, the arrangement was according to the sculptor's will, what posture the statue should take, what position in the cave was the most appropriate, and what position the donor was carved in, thus representing the donor's status.³ The female-centered Buddha statues carved on the north wall of the Huangfugong Cave are rare, and the appearance of this form may indicate the importance of women, reflected in the Buddha statues at that time.

In general, the statues of female donors carved in the Longmen Grottoes significantly increased compared with those in the Yungang Grottoes, especially the female Buddha statues in the Huangfugong Cave, which was unprecedented. It can also be seen that the colors of women in the Longmen Grottoes are stronger than those in the Yungang Grottoes.

2. Feminized Statues of Bodhisattvas

During the period of Emperor Xiaoming in the Longmen Grottoes, there were some statues of Bodhisattvas in feminine form. For example, there is a special statue in the Putai Cave—the Bodhisattva statue on the left side of the front wall. Its facial lines are soft, the mouth is raised, the smile is shallow, the eyebrows are thin and the eyes are trimmed, and the arm and fingers are round and soft, just like the image of a woman. In addition, there is the

Six Division Cave, where a statue niche is carved on the lion's south side in the south of the western wall. The niche has a Bodhisattva with a round arch (figure 10), 17 cm high×8 cm wide×2 cm deep. The Bodhisattva statue has a collar and wrist bracelet, with a scarf hanging on the side of the body in the left hand and a round object in the right hand.⁴ On the south side of the niche, a record of the niche's contents indicates that the niche's lord was a woman. Although the inscription does not indicate the time of the creation of the image, the age can be inferred from other forms of sculpture. There are three pairs of six Dharma protection lions squatting in the Six Division Cave, which is located in front of the three main Buddha seats; curved engraved lines represent the lions's hair. This kind of lion shape was very popular in the later period of Emperor Xuanwu. Since Emperor Xiaoming's ShenGui reign (518 AD), they either raised their feet or ran, with large dynamic characteristics.⁵

The arch Bodhisattva on the south side of the Liushidong Lion has obvious feminine characteristics, and the inscriptions on the statues indicate that the statue master is a woman. The posture of this Bodhisattva is somewhat similar to that of the Guan Yin statue made by Bhikshuni Zhenzhi (真智) in the second year of Yonglong (681 AD), located outside the Wanbuddha Cave in the Longmen Grottoes. The statue of Bodhisattva is 85 cm high, with its head slightly tilted to the right, its hair high and tied up, its eyes slightly dozed, its face round, its left hand holding the bottle naturally drooping, its right arm bending to brush the dust on its right shoulder, its dust tail hanging down behind it, and its whole body decorated with a necklace, scarf, arm steel, etc. The Bodhisattva's posture presents an "S" shape on the platform, vividly displaying feminine softness.⁶ Yin Xieli (尹協理) and Wen Jinyu (溫金玉) commented, "This can be regarded as the representative work of female goddess Guan Shiyin."⁷ As for this Bodhisattva statue created by Bhikshuni Zhenzhi, Gong Dazhong thought it had little to do with the Ten Thousand Buddha Cave, but it was indeed a statue of the Tang Dynasty.

It is no coincidence that the statue of Kitawaki Bodhisattva in the third grotto of the Gongxian Grottoes Temple also shows feminine characteristics. Standing on the platform, this bodhisattva has a long and slender figure, a calm face and a slight smile, which seems to have the spirit charm of a girl and a hint of mystery, which is no different from the miraculous actions of ordinary women in the world.

The distance between the Longmen Grottoes, where the Putai Cave and the Liushi Cave are located, and Gongxian Grottoes Temple is not more than a few tens

of kilometers; both are near the city of Luoyang, and the statues carved in the Gongxian Grottoes Temple can also prove their relationship with imperial power. According to historical documentation, some scholars speculate that Cave 3 of the Gongxian Grottoes Temple was built for Emperor Xiaoming and his empress, which began in the second year of Xiping (517 AD) or later and was completed in the late year of Xiaochang in 528 AD.⁸ The first cutting stage of the Putai Cave is roughly defined in the Northern Wei Dynasty as being between the Zhengguang and Xiaochang years (520-527 AD); the Liushi Cave was dug in the period of Emperor Xiaoming. The Putai Cave and the third cave of the Gongxian Grottoes were excavated at a similar time, in which statues of Bodhisattva women appeared. The Bodhisattvas in the Putai Cave and the Liushi Cave are round, compared with the Bodhisattvas in Gave 3 in the Gongxian Grottoes; the image is slightly thin, and the face is beautiful. There is a succession relationship between the Longmen Grottoes and the Gongxian Grottoes Temple, and the feminine characteristics of Bodhisattvas may imitate each other. Some studies believe that the Buddha statues in the Northern Dynasty show feminine characteristics, which may be related to the “Xianghao” (相好) in Buddhist sutras. The Xianghao of the Buddha is also the solemn physical

Figure 10. This statue of Bodhisattva was erected in the Sixth Division Cave. From *Chinese Grottoes: Longmen Grottoes 1*.

appearance of the Buddha; “The thirty-two major marks of a great man and the eighty excellent characteristics that accompany him” is a detailed description of the Buddha’s appearance. The content of Xianghao is very complicated, and it is for this reason that the world has a realistic reference to the Buddha’s appearance in the Buddhist world.⁹ In addition, there may be other explanations for the presence of feminine Bodhisattvas in the Longmen Grottoes.

3. The Reasons for the Prevalence of Feminized Statues in the Longmen Grottoes

The emergence of so many female statues in the Longmen Grottoes is closely related to the political changes in the Northern Wei Dynasty. After the Northern Wei moved the capital to Luoyang, the nominal supreme ruler was Emperor Xiaoming, but Empress Dowager Hu controlled the actual power of the government.

Empress Dowager Hu, historically known as the Xuanwu Ling Empress, was the biological mother of Emperor Xiaoming Yuan Xu. In March of the third year of Yongping, Hu gave birth to Emperor Yuan Xu, breaking the old system of “the son of the noble mother dies” in the Northern Wei Dynasty, and was promoted to noble concubine. In the fourth year of Yanchang (515 AD), Yuan Xu ascended the throne at the age of five in the Luoyang Imperial Palace and because the emperor was too young the government was initially controlled by Yu Zhong; half a year later Emperor Xiaoming’s birth mother Empress Dowager Hu, with the support of the imperial family, deposed Yu Zhong and came to the court to rule. After the dictatorship, Empress Dowager Hu still ordered the exercise of power in the name of Your Monarch, and later the ministers also called her Your Monarch in a letter; she called herself Zhen (朕).¹⁰ In the first year of Zhengguang (520 AD), Yuan Cha (元叉) staged a coup d’état and imprisoned Empress Dowager Hu, ruling the government arbitrarily for five years. Under the control of Yuan Cha, the social contradictions of the Northern Wei regime intensified rapidly, and rebellions broke out in six towns. In the first year of Xiaochang, Empress Dowager Hu succeeded in the restoration of her position, with the support of the imperial kings, and once again came to the court to rule. In 528 AD, Empress Dowager Hu and the young lord were drowned in the Yellow River by Erzhuorong, ending Emperor Xiaoming’s era.¹¹

Empress Dowager Hu initially entered the palace due to her affinity with Buddhism. Later, during her period of governance, she expended substantial financial and

human resources to promote Buddhist activities. In the third year of Xiping, Hu Guozhen passed away. Empress Dowager Hu issued an edict stating, “From the day of him passing until the forty-nine day, a thousand monks are to hold fasting rituals, and seven individuals are to ordain as monks. On the hundredth day, ten thousand monks are to hold fasting rituals, and twenty-seven individuals are to ordain as monks.”¹² In the first year of Shengui, Empress Dowager Hu dispatched the Bhikshu Huisheng from the Chongli Monastery to the Western Regions to acquire Buddhist scriptures. In addition, there were numerous endeavors to establish temples and promote Buddhist activities. *Wei Shu* summarizes Empress Dowager Hu’s Buddhist undertakings: “Empress Dowager Ling was fervent in promoting Buddhist activities. She initiated the construction of temples such as Yongning Temple and Taishang Temple in the capital city, with substantial efforts and expenditures. In various provinces, she sponsored the creation of Buddhist images of the five ranks. Furthermore, she frequently organized fasting rituals, extending her charitable offerings to tens of thousands.”¹³ In the first year of Shengui, Yuan Cheng submitted a memorial stating that the trend of temple construction had become excessive, “Since the capital’s relocation, more than twenty years have passed, and temples have encroached upon residential areas, taking up as much as one-third.”¹⁴ From this, it can be observed that during Empress Dowager Hu’s reign, there was a widespread surge in the establishment of temples by the populace.

Simultaneously, the sculptural activities within the Longmen Grottoes also reached their zenith. The author sorted out the materials and found that the activity track of female statue-making is consistent with the change of the regime of Empress Dowager Hu. In the period of Emperor Xiaoming in the Longmen Grottoes (515-528 AD), there were thirty-two niches of female statues, and only six niches were carved by men for women. Looking at the overall chronology of these female niches, before the first year of Xiaochang, there were ten niches funded by women, of which three were joint ventures between men and women, and the remaining nineteen niches were carved after Empress Dowager Hu returned to power. Through the proportion of women depicted in the statues in the grottoes, we can infer the influence of Empress Dowager Hu’s regime on the social life of women.

During the reign of Empress Dowager Hu, women became the main subject of statue-making activities in the grottoes, and the feminine statues in the grottoes showed a different form. For example, the costumes and

hairstyles of the female providers are diversified, the division of different classes in the providers queue is no longer obvious, the female provider’s figure has a special presentation in the providers queue, and the aesthetic characteristics of Bodhisattva statues also show a feminine tendency. Whether the feminization of the statues in the grottoes is related to Empress Dowager Hu’s Buddhist activities can be compared and analyzed from the statues in the Yongning Temple. The influence of political activities on the feminization of statues is reflected in the cave statues and the small statues.

The pagoda of the Yongning Temple in Luoyang can be called a monument to the personal power of Empress Dowager Hu. Construction of the temple began in the first year of Xiping (516 AD) and was completed in three years. *Wei Shu* recorded: “In August two years, the Empress Dowager Ling visited the pagoda of Yongning Temple and climbed nine floors of floating pictures.”¹⁵ *The Buddhist temples in Luoyang* also record: “After the decoration was completed, Emperor Ming and the Empress Dowager ascended it together. They viewed the palace as if it were within their grasp, overlooking the capital city as if it were their household. Through their eyes, the palace was observed. People were forbidden

Figure 11. The head of the maid at the base of the Yongning Temple tower. From *Clay statues unearthed from Yongning Temple in the Northern Wei Dynasty*.

Figure 12. Female donor figures under niche S26 in the Lotus Cave. From *Cave 712 of Longmen Grottoes*.

Figure 13. Two clay statues from the Yongning Temple. From *Clay statues unearthed from Yongning Temple in the Northern Wei Dynasty*.

from ascending without permission.”¹⁶ When Emperor Xiaoming was only nine years old in the second year of the Divine Turtle, the Empress Dowager took her young lord to ascend the Pagoda, and the significance of her act was to “transform the public building, which was originally a symbol of national politics and a function of religious worship, into a work commemorating the ascent to the pinnacle of power.”¹⁷ The pagoda of the Yongning Temple, built by Empress Dowager Hu, was

Figure 14. The author hand-painted figures of worshipers under niche N246 of the Guyang Cave.

Figure15. The statue of Bodhisattva is on the front wall of the Putai Cave (right), and the statue of Bodhisattva is on the side of the Gongxian Grotto Temple (left).

brilliant for a time, representing the highest level of statues in the Northern Wei Dynasty during that period. The clay statues found from the existing sites are exquisite and beautiful in shape, more exquisite, delicate and vivid than the statues in the grottoes of the same period.¹⁸ The Yongning Temple's base site excavated a large number of donor statues, and the excavation briefing records: "small clay statues unearthed more than 300 pieces, mostly attached to the wall of the shadow sculpture", "head, generally 7 cm long, the neck can be inserted into the body of the image", "It's handmade, the clay is fine, and the molding is exquisite".¹⁹ In the Guyang Cave and the Lotus Cave of the Longmen Grottoes, a large number of statues of female providers are carved. They have different identities, and the most common statue is the maid with a double bun. Among the statues unearthed at the base of the Yongning Temple, there is also a head with a comb, 6.4 cm high, with the front of the hair parted on both sides and the top of the head with a comb in a loop hanging on both sides. The facial shape is round, with curved thin eyebrows, long thin eyes, tightly closed lips, and the face is naturally relaxed with a smile (figure 11). By comparison, the hairstyles of the existing female donors under the S26 niche in the Lotus Cave are similar to those of the maids unearthed in the Yongning Temple (figure

Figure 16. Buddha statue was unearthed from the base of the Yongning Temple. From *Clay statues unearthed from Yongning Temple in the Northern Wei Dynasty*.

12). In addition, there is a female head with a single petal bun unearthed from the Yongning Temple; the head is 8.4 cm high, the hair in front of the forehead is naturally separated, the top of the head is a petal style, the face is round, the eyebrows are smiling, and the female is gentle and elegant. Similar hairstyles are found in cave carvings, such as the female providers carved under niche No. N87 of the Lotus Cave and niche No. W141 of the Guyang Cave. Although No. N87 niche has no inscription; it is inferred from the clothing worn by women that it should be the Northern Wei Dynasty, and the date of the W141 niche is the sixth year of the Western Wei Dynasty (540 AD), which shows that this petal-like bun was quite popular in the Northern Wei Dynasty.

The female provider figures carved in the Longmen Grottoes are similar in dress, hairstyles, and heads un-earthed in the Yongning Temple. For example, of two clay statues unearthed in the Yongning Temple (figure 13), the first one is missing the head and feet, the residual height is 19.5 cm, the body is slender and has obvious curve changes, the lining of a long skirt drags the ground, the waist is broad, the outer cloth is dropped from the shoulders behind the body, the clothing sculpture is delicate, and the dynamic beauty is very beautiful. The second piece is a positive statue; the

Figure 17. The hands of Bodhisattva in the Putai Cave.

residual height is 19.3 cm, the head is missing, and the figure is wearing a cross-collar wide-sleeved long dress; this statue is slightly plump, and the original sculpture should be the image of nobility. Through comparison, it can be seen that the costumes of the donors under the N246 niche in the Guyang Cave and the S41 niche in the Lotus Cave are roughly the same as the costumes in the Yongning Temple. The texture and dynamic presentation of the costumes are roughly similar (figure 14).

In addition to the clothing of the offeror figure, the Bodhisattva figure also has similarities. The Bodhisattva statue on the wall of the Putai Cave is similar in appearance to a Bodhisattva head unearthed at the base of the Yongning Temple. The head of this Bodhisattva has a broken bun and is 21.8 cm high, with a plump and round face, curved and slender eyebrows, eyes shaped like willow leaves, small mouth and thin lips, and a slight smile on the mouth. The Bodhisattva statue in the Putai Cave also has a round face and a soft and comfortable smile (figure 15, figure 16). In addition to the likeness of the face, the hand features of the Bodhisattva statues have a high degree of similarity. By comparing the hand of Bodhisattva Wizhi in the Putai Cave with the clay statue of Buddha's hand in the base of the Yongning Temple, the middle ring finger is naturally curved and holds a peach-shaped or circular object, the index finger and little finger are naturally extended, and the hand shape is round and full and stretches naturally (figure 17, figure 18).²⁰

According to the records in the *Buddhist temples in Luoyang*, in the first year of Xiping, the Empress Dowager Hu established the Yongning Temple, with more than a thousand monk rooms and a nine-story wooden pagoda.²¹ After completing the Yongning Temple, Empress Dowager Hu expanded the temple many times, including building the Yongning Temple tower, using tens of thousands of people. Zhang Yi and Guo Anxing participated in this: "Yongning Temple pagoda construction, manufacturing design and other aspects are complicated, the Empress Dowager Ling once came to this place to guide the construction, as long as the question, Zhang Yi listened to the Empress Dowager's instructions to repair, no matter what aspect did not fall behind."²² From this, it can be inferred that the various aspects of construction at the Yongning Temple were all commissioned by Empress Dowager Hu. The completion of the Yongning Temple Pagoda took only sixteen years, and in the second month of the third year of Yongxi (534 AD), it was struck by lightning and caught fire. "The fire originated from the eighth level and quickly spread at dawn. There was thunder, rain, and darkness at that time, accompanied by mixed hail and snowfall. People from all

walks of life gathered to watch the fire, and the sounds of sorrow and mourning resonated throughout the capital." Based on this, it can be speculated that the completion of various statues within the Yongning Temple, at the latest, was by the third year of Yongxi (534 AD). Judging from the timeline of sculpting at the Yongning Temple and the Longmen Grottoes, it can be observed that there are female figurative sculptures carved between 516 and 534 AD within various caves such as the Guyang Cave, the Lotus Cave, and the Putai Cave.

The female donors carved under the statue niches in the grottoes are another manifestation of the appearance of women in society at that time. When artisans carved the donor figures, they must have followed the copy. Where did the copy come from? Some scholars analyzed it or it came from the prototype of the temple statue.²³ During the reign of Empress Dowager Hu, the establishment of temples far surpassed the creation of cave sculptures. "The cruelty of the He Yin (河陰) led many of the deceased court officials' families to abandon their residential properties and donate them for the use of monks and nuns, resulting in the transformation of a number of urban residences into temples within the capital city." It can be seen that the phenomenon of donating houses to temples was common at that time. The female statues in Luoyang during the Northern Wei

Figure 18. Clay Buddha hand statues at the base of the Yongning Temple pagoda. From *Clay statues unearthed from Yongning Temple in the Northern Wei Dynasty*.

Dynasty were concentrated during the reign of Empress Dowager Hu. The pagoda of the Yongning Temple was built with the support of Empress Dowager Hu, and the Buddha statues unearthed in the temple have high similarities with the feminine statues in the Longmen Grottoes, which is probably the result of the indirect influence of the temple statues on the statues in the Longmen Grottoes.

Conclusion

In the activities of making statues in the Longmen Grottoes during the Northern Wei Dynasty, there were a large number of niches made by the common people, among which the forms of statues with female colors were gradually enriched. From the Guyang Cave excavated in the early period to the Lotus Cave, to the Huangfugong Cave and the Putai Cave that were gradually excavated later, it can be seen that women played an indispensable role in statue-making activities

through the number, arrangement and combination of female donors and the feminization tendency of statues. The strong feminization in the grottoes indirectly reflects the change in the social status of women in the Northern Wei Dynasty. In addition, the side of the statues in the grottoes is also the reflection of political changes. Through comparison, the feminine features of the statues in the Longmen Grottoes are highly similar to the features of the statues unearthed in the Yongning Temple. As the monument of the personal regime of Empress Dowager Hu, the layout design and decorative style of the Yongning Temple were all inspired by Empress Dowager Hu.

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ENDNOTES

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龍門石窟北魏造像的女性化表現及原因

鄭曉雪

摘 要：在北魏時期，洛陽龍門石窟繼大同雲岡石窟之後開鑿。龍門石窟北魏造像與雲岡石窟相比，較為突出的表現就是其造像形式呈現出了不同的女性化特徵。首先，原本雕鑿於造像題記兩側的供養人像是男女相對應的，在石窟中出現了特別的排列方式；其次，皇甫公窟出現了以女性為中心的禮佛圖；最後，洞窟中雕鑿的菩薩像呈現出女性化的特徵等。龍門石窟女性造像興盛的時期正是胡太后個人權力極度膨脹的時期，並且當時寺院營建也極為盛行。同一時期，龍門石窟女性化造像與永寧寺塔出土的佛像有諸多相似之處，石窟造像與寺院營造皆是對當時社會風貌和政局變動的影射，造像的女性化表現很可能與胡太后政治權力的影響有關。

關鍵詞：龍門石窟；北魏；女性化造像；胡太后